

Teachers Awareness and Usability of Communication Technology in Christian Religious Studies Teaching and Learning for National Development

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Abstract

This write up is on the teachers' awareness and usability of Information and Communication Technology in Christian Religious Studies learning for national development. It was stated that information and communication technology ICT is the key in sustaining any development and no meaningful development can take place without the use of ICT. It is very clear that the introduction of information and communication technology in Christian Religious Studies learning has really brought remarkable improvement and change in the learning process. Among the challenges were resistance to change by teachers who have little or no knowledge of ICT, high cost of internet services in Nigerian and other financial constraints. The study also recommended that the use of ICT is still at the infant stage thus the schools administrators should provide support for effective use of ICT, Curriculum development should provide learning software and stimulation packages in all level of education in order to captivate learners to acquire the desired knowledge, government should improve on power supply and lick many more villages to the national electricity grid so as to encourage individual to learn and use the internet. It was concluded that judicious use of ICT materials to teach Christian Religious studies to boost learning and shaping humanity, molding their character and develop sound attitude and morality in the child.

Introduction

The 21st century human beings have witnessed an increase in the pursuit for knowledge, skills, information and competencies. Every aspect of human life has changed due the effects of science and technology. The use of modern technological tools has led to the increase of Information and Communication technology. In today's society, it is almost impossible for one to imagine that any society can survive without Information Communication Technology (ICT).¹ The upsurge of ICT technologies has its implications on school and education. It is not possible to ignore computers anymore. Education is faced with the challenge to incorporate computers and communication possibilities in a meaningful way. The role of technology in teaching and learning is rapidly becoming one of the most important and widely discussed in contemporary education policy. Most experts in education agree that, when properly used ICT holds great promise to improve teaching and learning.² A. S. Ariyo It has become, within a very short time, one of the basic building blocks of modern society. Many countries now regard understanding ICT and mastering its basic skills and concepts as part of the core of education, alongside reading, writing and numeracy. Africa has started witnessing the development of ICTs in various sectors health, games and sports, transportation, industries, fashion designing, and agriculture among others few years ago. The use of ICTs in education has contributed to the change from teacher-centred education system to learner centred education. Borrowing from the word "knowledge-Driven world" as conceived by Hawkins and Inwent, it means that education reform practices should focus on equal access and quality of education which should highlight the importance of change in the education sector through the use of ICT facilities and equipping new generations with enhanced skills to operate in the 21st century.³

The usability of information and communication technology ICT in teaching and learning Christian Religious Studies CRS is still an infant stage in Nigeria and Africa as a whole.⁴ ICT in Christian Religious Studies

teaching and learning that can improve efficiency and effectiveness of teaching and learning that can improve the quality of understanding and instruction. Christian Religious Studies CRS before lay emphasis on factual examination oriented approach and dogmas, today, has become a matter of investigation and experimental rather than indoctrination. The subject Christian Religious Studies (CRS) also occupies a very significant role in national Development and acts as a veritable tool for sustainable development. Nigeria cannot achieve its developmental goals without giving priority to the teaching and learning of Christian Religious Studies as it is the central means of changing at individual positively through the acquires of Christians values.⁵ It is often argued that for any nation to make progress, ICT must be well developed, but without the concept of “Knowing God”, scientific and technological concepts will be difficult to be understood. The Christian faith teaches that man cannot know God merely through natural revelation, which man rejected (Rom. 1:3) or through written revelation (the Holy Spirit), but a man knows God through an understanding and knowledge.⁶

Christian Religious Studies, according to Wiebe et al is one of most important subject which have played a significant role in the process of developing in the young people a kind moral behaviors desired by the adult of the society, consequently, honesty, truthfulness, obedience, respect for law and order, respect for elders and the sympathy for the welfare of their people is the concern of Christian religious studies. Therefore, it is necessary to teach CRS and develop knowledge and skills among students using ICT. Nigeria have commenced the act of updating their knowledge in computer literacy.⁷ Alabi also opined that, information. Such information can be accessed through the utilization of mobile cell phone, computer and internet. Information and Communication Technology is a digital technology used in storing, retrieving and disseminating information in the contemporary jet age.⁸ The various way use of ICT in teaching and learning CRS (CAL) Computer Assisted Learning, (CAR) Computer Assisted Research, (DL) Distance Learning and so on. The application of ICT packages like teleconferencing, video-conferencing among others help in presenting interactive instructional materials and the assessment of students

National Development

The national development is an “improvement in a country’s economic and social conditions”⁹ It is also to improve in the way of managing an area’s natural and human resources in order to create wealth and improve people’s lives. National development also demands that poverty and inequality of access to the good things of life be removed, it seeks to improve personal physical security and livelihoods and expansion of life chances. National development is usually taken to involves not only economic growth such as the GDP and GNP, but also some notion of equitable distribution, provision of good health care, education, housing and other essential services.¹⁰ National development as a process of emancipation of man from poverty, fear, exploitation, dirty environment, dependency on foreign financing and expertise.¹¹ It is the way of realistically finding political solution to peculiar needs in time and space of the people. In the context of this paper, it is the attainment of sufficient levels of economic growth and social wellbeing of the nation and its citizenry. National development is also seen as a multi-dimensional process involving the totality of man in his political, economic, psychological and social relations among other aspects of existence. Most a time, the concept of development has been misconstrued with infrastructural development such as roads, electricity, developing of industries among others. But national development surpasses these. Schumacher declares that national development does not start with goods but with people, therefore, development should be on the inculcation of quality of life of the its citizenry.¹² Nigeria as a nation to be able to attain total development, the implication of the foregoing is that, the educational system needs to provides people with qualitative functional literacy using every means including the use of educational technology.

Christian Religious Studies as a Goal for any National Development

Christian Religious Studies as a goal for any development in Nigeria will be analyses.

Economic Contribution

Production is one of the major sources of revenue in Nigeria. And the major foundation for the success of these businesses is the existence of peace and the inculcation of moral in every citizenry.¹³ Nigerians can travel from one place to another in any part of this country and the World for their business transactions because the Christian Religious Studies teach peace and tolerance for one another.¹⁴ The economists in Nigeria believes that teaching and learning of CRS is crucial for economic development as it helps them trade more widely. Christian religious studies is subjects been teaches in most of the schools in Nigeria to helps the citizenry obey the rule of law. A wide range of business categories in Nigeria including the banking industry, technology, the pharmaceutical industry and even vocational workers such as carpenters and electricians see increased need for CRS. Wadak adds that the government of Nigeria agreed that teaching CRS is one the key element of inculcating moral connection for new investment and bring national development.¹⁵

Political

Obieghu is of the view that politics in Nigeria would have been a difficult treat without the fear of God, the way of conducting political activities in Nigeria is through open rally campaigns to our teaming youth. Without teaching CRS it would be quite difficult if totally impossible to address a political audience at different rallies.¹⁶ CRS has made it possible and easy for different people to interact with one another. This alone has contributed to the existing unity in Nigeria. All the houses of assembly, members of houses representatives, the senate, judiciary and all other bodies in the nation find it easy to interact, tolerance, love through the teaching of CRS.

Education

The purpose of Education in Nigeria is for national unity and development, and it also believed that no nation can rise above the level of its education, for without education a nation cannot get the needed manpower required for material advancement and enlightenment of the citizenry. The trained teachers, medical doctors, lawyer's engineers among others are all products of education. This explains why it is argued that the quality of a nation's education determines the level of its national development.¹⁷ Garridau and Mwanti are of the view that teaching CRS is the corner stone of any educational process. It plays a vital role in education as it constitutes a subject and a foundation of learning, CRS of education in Nigeria contributes in no small way to the rapid development experienced in Nigeria.¹⁸

Importance of ICT in Education System

Presently, the education system all over the world has certainly been affected positively by the influence of information and communication technology (ICT). According to Abdul-Salaam, et al, information and communication technology has the potentials to accelerate, enrich, and deepen skill; to motivate and engage students in learning to help relate school experiences to work practices; to help create economic viability for tomorrow's workers, contribute to radical changes in Nigerians school; to strengthen teaching and to provide opportunities for connection between the school and the world. When we are looking at the role of education in nation building and the population explosion in schools today enforces, the use of ICT in teaching-learning process becomes imperative. Undoubtedly, the utilization of ICT by teachers will enhance effective teaching.¹⁹

Such issues like good course organization, effective class management, content creation, self-assessment self-study collaborative learning, task oriented activities, and effective communication between the actors of teaching learning process and research activities will be enhanced by the use of ICT based technology.²⁰ They are posited that, with the aid of ICT, teachers can take students beyond traditional limits, ensure their adequate participation in teaching and learning process and create vital environments to experiment and explore. This new development is a strong indication that the era of teachers without ICT skills are skills are gone.²¹ They are also added that, any classroom teacher with adequate and professional skills in ICT utilization will definitely have his students perform better in classroom learning.²³

ICT has made a very profound and remarkable impact on the quality and quantity of teaching, learning and research in the educational institutions. He has also indicated that, the pervasiveness of ICT has brought about rapid technological, social, political and economic transformation, which has eventuated in a network society organized around ICT. Yusuf has also been stressed that, ICT is an indispensable part of educational administration as its application makes institutions more efficient and productive, thereby engendering a variety of tools to enhance and facilitate teachers' pedagogical activities.²⁴ Yusuf also emphasized that, ICT utilization is the presentation and distribution of instructional content through web environment (e-teaching) or systems offering an integrated range of tools (stand-alone computer instruction, CD ROM amongst others) to support learning and communication. Instructional service delivery has to do with teaching/learning activities that take place in the classrooms.

Teachers and ICT Usage in CRS Classroom Instruction

There are several evidences that, ICT can be an effective tool in supporting teaching and learning process in the classroom. However, its introduction into schools does not by itself improve the quality of education or raise students attainment (Hennessy et.al, 2010). Effectively introducing technology into schools is also largely dependent upon the availability and accessibility of ICT resources (for example hardware, software and communications infrastructure). Clearly if technology cannot be accessed by the teacher, as in so many educational settings in Sub Sahara African countries, then it will not be used. These are predominantly ICT illiteracy and confidence among teachers, and education of subject teachers to assist them in integrating ICT into learning areas.²⁴

There are various types of ICT facilities that can be used in the teaching learning process in Nigerians schools. These are; radio, television, computers, overhead projectors, optical fibers, fax machines, CDRoms, Internet, electronic notice board, slides, digital multimedia, video/VCD machine and so on. It is most common that such facilities are not sufficiently provided for teaching – learning process in many secondary schools in developing countries. Fakeye points out that, in most of schools in Nigeria do not have computers, hence are not connected to the internet. He has also added that, those who have computers do not use them for teaching but solely for administrative purposes.²⁵ Adomi, et.al, indicated that lack of adequate search skills and of access points in the schools were reported as forces inhibiting the use of internet by secondary school teachers.²⁶

The study to explore factors that influence classroom use of ICT in Sub-Saharan Africa, was noted that, introducing technology into schools is largely dependent upon the availability and accessibility of ICT resources. It was observed that schools are increasingly being equipped with computers for teaching, learning and administrative purposes; connectivity is improving and students enthusiastic about using computers for learning despite lack of equipment available. They are also noted that, there are two main reasons why teachers use ICT. First, teachers feel that their own use of computers benefits the learners, and second, teachers feel learners benefit from using the computers themselves.²⁷ According to Ajayi, the use of ICT facilities, involves various method which include systematized feedback system, computer-based operation/network, video conferencing and audio conferencing, internet/ worldwide websites and computer assisted instruction. It must however be stressed that the effective use of the various method of the ICT in teaching leaning depends on the availability of these facilities and teachers' competence in using them.²⁸

Teachers need to be supported to get the most from using ICT in classrooms. The implementing of technological solutions need to ensure that they are context-specific, and adapted to local needs and conditions. It is also imperative that ICT programs are sustainable or effective by ensuring that the technologies embedded within them meet the demands of users in appropriate ways. It is essential that potential users have a sound understanding of how to use new ICTs beneficially, and a cultural view of the relationship between learning and technology.²⁹ There is a clear difference between teachers who choose ICT resources to enhance understanding of a particular topic, and those who choose resources merely to present students work in a new way without any direct application to the topic. The evidence shows that when teachers use their pedagogical knowledge both of

the subject and also of how students understand and learn the subject, they can then maximize the effects of using ICT in terms of increasing students' attainment.³⁰

Challenges of Using ICT in Teaching and Learning CRS in Nigerian Education System

ICT has a key role to play in enabling the education industry to manage complex information flows and to integrate them towards effective educational planning and national development. Although ICT holds great potentials in supporting and augmenting existing educational as well as national development efforts in Nigeria, several challenges remain. These challenges include:

1. Resistance to change from traditional pedagogical methods to more innovative, technological-based teaching and learning methods by both students and academics. The attitudes of various managements in and outside institutions towards the development of the ICT related facilities such as the internet and procurement of computers are rather slow in some instances, and in others there are no aids or support by the government at all.³¹ Inadequate ICT infrastructure including computer hardware and software and bandwidth/access.
2. Lack of qualified ICT personnel. Most institutions lack computer literate teachers and ICT experts that would support and manage the internet connectivity and/or application of computing in the teaching-learning process. The cost of equipment in a country like Nigeria with a battered economy and seriously devalued currency is enormous. However, it should be noted that the problem might not be fund nor the technology but the will on the part of government and/or the governors of education.³²
3. Nigeria lacks the necessary infrastructural facilities to benefit from ICT. Again, most of the ICT infrastructures such as the internet, telefax, and e-mail depend on NITEL (Nigerian Tele-communications Limited), NIPOST (Nigerian Postal Agency) and PHCN (Power Holding Corporation of Nigeria) services. These services are inadequate and they attract high bills.
4. Research shows that, many teachers do not have the necessary IT skills and feel uncomfortable, nor do they have the specific training needed to be able to use the new resources in the classroom, students' skill of using the technology is also a series challenge that needs the attention of the institutes.³³

Conclusion

ICT is increasingly being used to give learners access to information, promote interaction and communication and enhance tolerance. In order to maximize the potential of ICT in teaching and learning Christian religious studies, it is vital that the use of ICT is introduced and supported in a developing way, and also in a range of pedagogical approaches that will promote lifelong learning. Finally, technology promotes CRS subject teachers and learners with fresh authentic and motivating materials directly from the internet. ICT materials and resources really yield positive result in classroom. Challenge is posed on the limited access and availability of ICT tools and resources in teaching and learning of CRS subject. The pedagogy used while teaching and learning of CRS seemed to be quite appropriate as it was learner-centred. The pedagogy was integrated well with the use of ICT which appealed to the learners and made learning interesting thus having a positive impact on their attainment.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of the study:

1. Government should ensure that ICT materials are available in schools, to ensure effective learning of Christian Religious Studies.
2. Schools should be deliberate in training their teachers for certification in ICT for effective integration in teaching and learning.
3. Government should provide workshop, seminars and other programmes for teachers on the need of incorporating ICT in the teaching of Christian Religious Studies in secondary schools.

Lack of funds was identified as one of the major challenges; hence, it is recommended that the schools should give incentives to teachers for motivation. Individuals cooperate bodies and the government should assist in providing internet and sources of power to schools.

Endnotes

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